

AIAL Feedback to European Commission's AI Act High-Risk Targeted Consultation

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INTRODUCTION

This document represents the answers prepared by the team at AI Accountability Lab (AIAL) for the *Targeted Stakeholder Consultation on the Classification of AI Systems as High-Risk*¹, conducted by the European Commission's AI Office as part of its duties under the AI Act². The consultation was open for 6 weeks from 6th June until 18th July 2025, during which the AIAL team submitted its response.

The AIAL team sought to identify aspects of the AI Act's high-risk criteria and associated procedures that require clarification due to uncertainties regarding its scope, undefined terms, or contradictions regarding its own provisions and their interactions with the GDPR. As the scope of the AI Act's high-risk activities defined in Annex III is vast, we focused on questions related to Clause 3 regarding Education and Vocational Training institutions due to our familiarity with the processes and stakeholders involved.

This report provides an expanded version of the responses submitted during the consultation, with the intent to preserve their intended meaning while expanding on the details and clarifications as the original consultation imposed an extremely short character limit. Due to the focus on education domain for Annex III(3), only specific

¹<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/commission-launches-public-consultation-high-risk-ai-systems>

² Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act)
<http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj>

questions from Sections 2, 3, 4, and 5 of the consultation were selected (i.e. Questions 16, 33, 41, 42, 44, 51). The structure of the document follows the same format and order as the questions posed in the consultation, where each question is followed by the AIAL team's corresponding notes and responses.

ABOUT AIAL

The AI Accountability Lab (AIAL) is a dedicated research lab within Trinity College Dublin that is focused on ensuring that the wider AI ecology — from research and product development, to regulation — centres public interest, particularly, the most marginalised and disenfranchised in society. Our inquiries into AI accountability, therefore, span from studies of large systems, structures, and ecologies (such as the AI field itself and regulatory processes) to executions of audits and evaluations on specific AI models, tools, and training datasets.

We recognize that AI accountability research is most impactful when it can inform the public, impacted groups, and policy makers. Thus, we aim for active policy translation of our (as well as field wide) research.

You can find more information about the AIAL on its website at <https://aial.ie/>.

FEEDBACK SUBMITTED FOR TARGETED STAKEHOLDER CONSULTATION ON CLASSIFICATION OF AI SYSTEMS AS HIGH-RISK

Question 16. Questions in relation to Annex III of the AI Act Education and vocational training

If you see the need for clarification of the high-risk classification in *Point 3 of Annex III to the AI Act* and its interplay with other Union or national legislation, please specify the practical provision in other Union or national law and where you see need for clarification of the interplay

**Note: In national legislations the universities are given autonomy on which, how, and where procedures are implemented, except for a few instances such as centralised admissions. Therefore in our response, we primarily assume the university policies are relevant legislations for the purposes of this question.*

1. Our first and foremost question raises the important criteria regarding interplay with GDPR in terms of whether the AI Act's Anx.III(3) activities are:

(a) subject to the GDPR since all of them involve people and information about them (i.e. as data subjects and personal data); and

(b) whether these are to be considered as automated decision-making as they use AI which by definition represents automation and involve decision making in each

of their steps; and

(c) are the outcomes from these activities to be considered as 'legal effects' in context of the GDPR's Article 35(3a) which triggers the requirement to conduct a DPIA?

We believe these to be the case based on our analysis³ showing there is significant overlap between GDPR's DPIA required criterias (both in GDPR and at national levels) with the AI Act's Anx.III activities.

2. The high-risk activities in Anx.III(3) concern educational institutions, largely universities and schools. In Article 6(3), there are specific '*derogations*' through which activities are exempted from being classified as high-risk. We seek clarification on these, as they are currently permitted (i.e. not prohibited) by legislation governing the educational sector. The following comments and questions elaborate further on this.

3. In Anx.III(3)(a), it is unclear whether "*determine access or admissions or assigning to institution*" refers exclusively to initial admissions decisions or also to all subsequent determinations regarding students within the institution context, such as for course selection, access to facilities (e.g., exam halls, laboratories or libraries), or elective enrolments. For example, do AI systems used as part of security monitoring for entrance to a facility fulfill this criteria? Such systems may be used to determine whether to permit access, or to flag suspicious activity which may result in a denial of access, and consequently whether a student can enter or continue using a facility. Further, the expression "*able to access*" in Anx.III(3)(c) may also imply the same interpretation, where in this context, can "*level of education*" also include perks and facilities provided as part of the education or educational environment? E.g. a library facility or gym provided to the student as part of the educational process.

4. Anx.III(3)(b) addresses AI systems used for evaluating learning outcomes but does not specify the level at which such evaluations must occur to be considered high-risk. Evaluations may occur through a central examination (e.g., managed by the high-level board at university or school level) or through assessments conducted by individual instructors (e.g., by a lecturer at module or subject level, or individual assignments evaluated by teaching assistants). In this context, which activities are covered under the term '*evaluate*'? This clarification is necessary as all such assessments contribute wholly or in part towards the subsequent evaluation of learning outcomes as determined by the institution through its structuring of courses and programs.

5. In Anx.III(3)(d), the term "*tests*" require a similar clarification. Is "*testing*" limited to formal examinations governed by institutional policy, or does it also encompass informal assessments which are not administered as examinations but involve evaluation of students? Further, does the term "*tests*" also include evaluations,

³ Rintamäki, Tytti, Delaram Golpayegani, Dave Lewis, Edoardo Celeste, and Harshvardhan J. Pandit. 2025. "*Impact Assessment Requirements in the GDPR Vs the AI Act: Overlaps, Divergence, and Implications*" OSF Preprints. May 19. https://doi:10.31219/osf.io/6qhzj_v2

assignments, and tasks conducted at home or through online services without the presence of a "testing environment" which are increasingly commonly used at most schools and universities for managing submissions?

6. Anx.III(3)(d) also includes "*monitoring*" and "*prohibited behaviour*" with an emphasis on "test" situations – which are not clearly defined but are presumed to be the examinations administered as part of educational courses. However, monitoring for prohibited behaviour can also occur outside of these test situations. For example, during lectures when students are performing an evaluation but which is not part of the formal school or university examination processes. Further monitoring may also occur in areas surrounding the test location with the purpose of detecting external interference, such as cheating assistance (e.g. to detect a person signalling from outside, or to identify students hiding objects to take into the exam room), or as part of security arrangements (e.g. for anti-bullying or to ensure belongings kept outside the room are safely stored). Such use of monitoring, typically carried out through CCTV systems, raises the necessity of broadening the interpretation of 'test' as any evaluation undertaken by the students regardless of their location. Further, all monitoring associated with a 'test', regardless of whether it is directly monitoring students within the exam room, should be considered in scope of this clause as the intent here is to categorise these systems as high-risk due to their impact on the students. This should be clarified in the guidelines.

7. Anx.III(3)(d) refers to the monitoring of "*prohibited behavior*", but does not define the scope and criteria used to determine the prohibition. For example, are prohibitions referred to here the same as those outlined in Article 5 of the AI Act? Or is it sufficient for the university to declare an activity or behaviour as being prohibited during a test and then use an AI system to monitor whether this occurs?

8. In Anx.III(3)(d), the term "*behaviour*" requires further clarification as it is unclear as to what it constitutes. Does "*behaviour*" refer solely to observable physical actions and the interpretation of intent or expressed actions? Or does it also include inferred mental states and internal thoughts? The latter is not based on factual evidence or has a valid scientific basis, but instead risks AI systems being used for implementing pseudo-science and phrenology. For example, would an AI system that generates a score representing the potential for a student to cheat in an exam, without directly observing or detecting any specific physical behaviour of cheating and without an established valid scientific basis for deriving this state of mind, be acceptable for this criteria as it seems to fit the criteria for "*prohibited behaviour*" used in this clause? Further, the phrasing "*during tests*" implies that such high-risk systems only occur when the AI system is used in the venue (i.e. real-time or during the period of exam). However, the same risks still persist if the AI system is used after the tests e.g. by recording a video during the test and analysing it afterwards, or even when assessing

the answer scripts, or by monitoring the student's activities. Therefore, such interpretations should be clarified in the guidelines and the use of phrenological basis for behaviours should be prohibited and prevented from being legitimised by the AI Act rather than being left to be implemented and then investigated.

9. For the exemptions Under Article 6(3), several terms used in Article 6(3) needs clarification:

- (a) In Article 6(3)(a), what does "*procedural*" mean? Does it refer exclusively to formally documented institutional procedures, or does it also include discretionary practices (e.g., where a lecturer or a teacher carried out an activity in relation to an assignment)? If the former, then can an university simply document a task as procedural i.e. part of its documented set of processes, in order to avail of this exemption?
- (b) In Article 6(3)(a), what does "*narrow*" mean? No clear criteria are provided to assess whether a task is "*narrow*." What criteria or test should be applied to make this determination? Further, the phrasing of "*narrow*" contains an implied assumption that the scale or scope of the risks are reduced, which may not be true. Therefore, the meaning of narrow should be clarified in a way that does not permit its use despite high-risk existing in specific cases.
- (c) In Article 6(3)(b), does "*previously completed human activity*" mean the human completes the activity first and then the AI system is used to extend the outcome or decision, and this classifies for exemption? For this to satisfy the condition that such use does not "*materially influence the outcome of decision-making*" is it necessary that the outputs from the use of AI not be used again in this or subsequent processes?
- (d) In Article 6(3)(b): What does "*improve*" mean? Is merely having an intent to improve sufficient, or must there be demonstrable evidence (qualitative or quantitative) of actual improvement in outcomes? For instance, consider a scenario in which a lecturer first grades assignments manually and subsequently uses an AI system to re-evaluate the same submission. Does "*improvement*" refer to measurable changes in scores, or is it enough for the lecturer to perceive the AI as offering greater fairness or consistency across students? And in such cases, does the use of this score towards evaluation meet the criteria for "*materially influencing the outcome of decision making*" i.e. the output of the AI system used in this manner satisfies the criteria of decision making (e.g. as established in the GDPR)?
- (e) Article 6(3)(c) implies the above (i.e. 8d) should not be used to "*replace or influence the previously completed assessment without proper human review*" – however the phrasing of the second subparagraph states that "*any of the following conditions*" must be fulfilled, which means Article 6(3)(b) and Article

- 6(3)(c) have a potential conflict as 6(3)(b) intends to change a prior outcome without a human review whereas 6(3)(c) requires a human review.
- (f) In Article 6(3)(d), what does a "*preparatory task*" mean? What is the test to determine whether a task or a part of the process is preparatory as opposed to other phases? For example, in Anx.III(3)(a) if an AI system calculates a score that is later considered by a human decision-maker during admissions or grading, is this truly "*preparatory*" if the score influences the outcome? Does this meet the criteria of "*materially influencing the outcome of decision making*"? Secondly, if such systems generate incorrect outputs (e.g., hallucinated student data, unfair scores), and these outputs affect decision-making in areas covered by Anx.III(3) (e.g. admissions, assessments, behavioural monitoring), this exemption would allow such uses to be carried out without being high-risk as they meet the criteria in Article 6(3)(d) as long as the task is justified to be '*merely preparatory*'. For example, a student's submitted information is assessed by an AI system in relation to Anx.III(3) purposes, where the AI hallucinates or errs regarding the information in its output to a task that is considered preparatory. However, by definition, such preparatory tasks have a likely material influence on outcome of decision making as we presume all tasks in Anx.III(3) are forms of decision making (e.g. under GDPR). So by what criteria can a task be preparatory but not lead to materially influencing the outcome of decision making?
- (g) In the final subparagraph of Article 6(3), the criteria for high-risk is established as whenever *profiling* occurs in the context of Anx.III. Referring to Anx.III(3), the purposes specified in 3(a) and 3(c) are highly likely, if not always, to include profiling as they require information on the person in the form of a profile to complete the task. Does this mean that these two purposes are unlikely to be exempted under Article 6(3)? The guidelines should clarify when profiling occurs in a high-risk scenario described in Annex III, and consequently its inability to be exempted through Article 6(3).

Question 33.

What aspects of the definition of the intended purpose, as outlined in Article 3(12) AI Act, need additional clarification? *Please specify the concrete elements and the issues for which you need further clarification; please provide concrete examples*

1. The AI Act defines '*intended purpose*' (Arts. 3-12) as "*the use for which an AI system is intended by the provider, including the specific context and conditions of use, as specified in the information supplied by the provider in the instructions for use, promotional or sales materials and statements, as well as in the technical*

documentation". However, it does not clarify what exact and specific information this can constitute, which leaves the actual intended purpose open to interpretation.

Based on our prior research⁴ we think this definition needs additional clarification in context of defining intended purposes based on specific purposes being mentioned in other parts of the AI Act as:

- (a) Purpose(s) for which an AI system was developed (Article 3(3));
- (b) Purpose(s) for which the AI system was put on the market (Article 3(9));
- (c) Purpose(s) of data collection for AI systems developed and operated with personal data (Article 10(2)(b));

2. Given the definition of intended purpose is crucial to several key obligations of the AI Act, it is important to clarify the following:

- (a) To what extent can the intended purpose of an AI system be determined based on vendors' marketing materials or technical documentation from a previous version? Specifically, is merely updating the version number of the AI system a sufficient means to discard previous marketing and sales materials and assert a different intended purpose even if the underlying AI system itself has not had any major changes? Can this be a measure to change or discard prior marketed claims that are false or problematic without re-evaluating whether the system's functionality or scope has materially changed? Further, how should marketing claims and sales materials that are not tied to a specific version of the AI System (e.g. claims made on a broad scale regarding a product line or a brand) be included in the interpretation of intended purposes? How far back in time should such claims be evaluated?
- (b) Does the intended purpose also include use cases and testimonials from customers or vendors that demonstrate the technology being used differently from what is described in the official instructions for use and technical documentation? For example, if an AI system is advertised on a website as capable of performing tasks based on how specific customers have applied it rather than through direct claims made by the manufacturer or provider. Such representations are still considered "promotion" within the framework of business management and marketing, and therefore should they also be considered as part of the intended purpose? Following from such interpretations, shall the deployer's marketing and sales materials, for example on their own website or as a testimonial on the provider's website showing how they have been using the AI system, also be taken into account to understand

⁴ Pandit, H. J., & Rintamäki, T. (2025). *Towards an automated AI Act FRIA tool that can reuse GDPR's DPIA* [Preprint]. OSF Preprints. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/538wy>

whether their use constitutes a change in the intended purpose as per Article 25(1)(c) and therefore makes them a provider?

Question 41.

Are there aspects related to the AI Act's obligations for deployers of high-risk AI systems for the fundamental rights impact assessment for which you would seek clarification in the template?

1. Article 27(1)(a) AI Act requires that deployers of high-risk AI systems provide “*a description of the deployer’s process for deciding to use the system and the use itself, including the persons who are likely to be affected by the use of the system*”. However, the AI Act does not define what “*description of the deployer’s process*” means. Therefore, what precisely does the description in Article 27(1)(a) entail? And what is the source of this information (e.g. in other AI Act obligations)?
2. The FRIA process, as currently outlined, does not allow the deployer or the organisation to use the results to mitigate the risks or to change the implementation of the AI system in a way that mitigates the risks. Instead, Article 27(3) requires the deployer to notify the MSA of the results “*once the assessment ... has been performed*”. In comparison, the GDPR's Article 35 procedures for a DPIA provide multiple pathways where the controller may choose not to proceed with the processing activity, revise the measures and reconduct the DPIA, or consult the relevant Data Protection Authority (DPA). Clarification regarding a similar procedure should be provided so that the deployer is aware of these options and only chooses to inform the MSA if and when the AI system is still being intended to be put into operation after the FRIA (as per Article 27(1)).

Question 42. In your view, how can complementarity of the fundamental rights impact assessment and the data protection impact assessment be ensured, while avoiding overlaps?

1. Where and how should a DPIA be reused within a FRIA as intended in Article 27(4) which specifically refers to 'obligations' met through a prior DPIA? Specifically, should: a) the deployer not be required to conduct a FRIA if a DPIA already exists for the AI system? or, b) should the deployer not be required to repeat assessments already conducted in the DPIA, such as Article 27(4)(1)(c) regarding identification of affected individuals? or c) should the deployer reuse the DPIA with additional AI-specific risks in the AI Act's FRIA? Based on these, we foresee three methods for the harmonised utilisation of DPIA and FRIA without increasing the burden of obligations: a) DPIA

outcomes (i.e. identified risks and impacts) be used as input for the FRIA; b) the DPIA and FRIA be conducted simultaneously as a combined process which avoids repeating information and assessments; or c) shared components of the DPIA and FRIA be conducted together initially, with the remaining parts completed separately.

2. Article 27(4) explicitly acknowledges the reuse of DPIA as a ‘complement’ to the FRIA obligations, however, this is complicated by the lack of clarity in AI Act Article 27(1a) regarding the interpretation of “*a description of the deployer’s processes in line with its intended purpose*” in a manner that aligns with the interpretation of “*systematic description*” in Article 35(7a) GDPR for a DPIA. Therefore, to what extent can a deployer legitimately reuse a DPIA conducted by a provider or another entity within the AI value chain by relying on the risks and impacts identified in such prior assessments, particularly as the AI Act has its own definition of risks and specific prohibitions? Further, as per AI Act Articles 27(2) and 27(4), what should be the obligation of the deployer, who is reusing a DPIA from a provider or another actor in the value chain, in terms of accepting the outcomes of the assessment (i.e. accept the information as is) as compared to ensuring those outcomes have been derived appropriately (i.e. evaluate the assessment itself)? Compared to the GDPR where the DPIA is specifically the controller's responsibility, the AI Act only refers to the existence of the DPIA in Article 27(4) without clarifying its origin or the responsibility of the provider or deployer in relation to the DPIA. The guidelines should clarify that the DPIA referred to in Article 27(4) is an assessment conducted by the same entity as that who is carrying out the FRIA.

3. The phrasing of Article 27(4) implies that the overlap between the DPIA and FRIA will be occasional. However, our research (“*High-Risk Categorisations in GDPR vs AI Act: Overlaps and Implications*” https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/6qhzj_v2) shows that the GDPR applies and a DPIA is required in almost all of the Anx.III activities based on an analysis of DPIA required processing activities in GDPR, EDPB guidelines, and at national levels as per GDPR Article 35(4). We therefore request that the FRIA template and guidance include, by default, the obligations and procedures for a DPIA with the option to not utilise them in cases where a DPIA is not necessary which can be explained through a justification as evidence. Further, as there is an overlap between DPIA and FRIA requirements for use-cases, we request that the FRIA templates be complimentary with existing DPIA templates to avoid repetitive form-filling for two regulations, and that the “*mitigation measures*” referred to AI Act be documented and evaluated together with those from the GDPR in a complimentary manner.

Question 44. Do you have any feedback on issues that need clarification as well as practical examples on the application of the concept of 'substantial modification' to a high-risk AI system.

1. We request clarification on what should be considered as "*substantial modification*" as its definition is based on "*change*" (Article 3(23)). In particular, the clarification should indicate what should this change be based on or how it should be detected in the context of AI systems as defined under the AI Act. If we consider that the change is based on the definition of intended purpose, what specific information criteria should be assessed to determine change? Our work can be helpful here: "*Towards An Automated AI Act FRIA Tool That Can Reuse GDPR's DPIA*" <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/538wy> as it clarifies the information elements from other articles of the AI Act which can be relied upon to form the intended purpose description, and where changes in this existing information can trigger the obligation to detect whether the modification is substantial.

Question 51. Do you consider that some of the use cases listed in Annex III require adaptation in order to fulfil the conditions laid down pursuant to Article 7(3) AI Act and should therefore **be amended** and should be integrated into the assessment pursuant to Article 112(1) AI Act?

Please justify why you consider that the use case needs to be adapted in order to fulfil the conditions as per Article 7(3) AI Act

1. Yes, we consider that the use-cases listed in Anx.III, particularly those under point (3) relating to education, are too vague and ambiguously defined to reliably determine their applicability in specific institutional contexts such as universities and schools despite appearing to be designed with these environments in mind. The primary challenge comes from the difference in terminologies, where Anx.III(3) uses terms that are different from the organisational terms used to describe and document the intended activities. To preempt lengthy interpretation rhetorics and potential case law establishment just to clarify the meaning on terms, we recommend that Anx.III clauses be further expanded with a list of specific cases that explicitly use the terminologies as currently used by organisations to cover such use-cases. For example, Anx. III(3)(b) uses "learning outcomes" as a broad term as it is also present in educational policies, but the specific activities used to perform this in a school or university would include "exams", "tests", and "assignments" with the purpose of evaluating students. Similarly, "steer" is also vague and should be clarified to indicate that the AI systems are used

directly or indirectly to provide feedback, perform assessments or calculate scores, or determine qualifications – which are associated with learning outcomes.

CONCLUSION

After analyzing and responding to selected questions from the consultation prepared by the European Commission, this report draws conclusions from two perspectives: (i) the structure of the consultation; and (ii) inconsistencies in the legislation regarding definitions, scope, and its capacity to interact with other regulations.

The structure of the consultation led to a reordering of the responses originally submitted in the form. Due to the character limit imposed, the responses had to remain concise and could not provide detailed elaboration despite its urgent necessity. It is important to stress the need to increase this limit, allowing stakeholders to present suggestions, observations, and criticisms of the AI Act in a more comprehensive manner. The same applies to the scope of the questions, which restricted the breadth of the analysis and prevented examination of other relevant aspects due to the limited scope of the questions and the inability to provide additional information.

In relation to the substance of the responses, the report outlines how the AI Act lacks precise definitions and instead relies upon 'vague' terms that have no clear criteria or defined legal interpretation. Furthermore, certain terms are used in a manner that is overly broad or ambiguous, creating room for interpretations that could undermine the very objectives of the regulation, and possibly also leading to loopholes that seem to permit activities without necessary obligations.

Finally, we draw attention to the urgent need to address these issues by providing greater clarity regarding the interpretation and regulation of high-risk AI systems to ensure effective and consistent application of the law.